

Adsorption of Carbon Tetrachloride Vapour by Carbon Blacks and Activated Carbons

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Adsorption of carbon tetrachloride vapour at 35° on five carbon blacks and six activated carbons has been studied. Adsorption in each case is reversible as sorption-desorption isotherms almost superimpose. This adsorption which constitutes an important, though empirical, test in quality control determinations has a significance in estimating specific surface areas of non-porous carbons, like carbon blacks only. Its relevance in the case of activated carbons, however, is limited to approximation of relative proportion of ultrafine micropores in the porous networks of these systems.

ADSORPTION of carbon tetrachloride vapour at ambient temperature by carbons constitutes an important laboratory test in quality control determinations^{1, 2}. The test, however, is empirical and it is not known what it actually measures. On account of rather high molecular area (36.6Å²) of the adsorbate, it is doubtful if the test can be used as an index of specific surface area or pore volume of the adsorbate. Berezkin *et al*³ determined adsorption isotherms of carbon tetrachloride at different temperatures up to 65° on a carbon black of surface area equal to 85 m²/g. The surface coverage, as determined by applying Hill and deBoer equation⁴, was found to extend up to about 40 per cent of monolayer only. Adsorption isotherms on non-porous kaolin and magnesia⁵ were found to be of Type III. The values of surface area obtained by applying B.E.T. equation were found to be in fair agreement with those obtained from the isotherms of oxygen determined at -183° in the case of coarser fractions of kaolin⁵ only. There appears to be no such comparative information with regard to carbon blacks or activated carbons. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

Experimental

Five well known carbon blacks and six commercial activated carbons, labelled as A, B, D, E, G and H, were used in the present investigations. Carbon tetrachloride was of A.R. (B.D.H.) quality. Adsorption-desorption isotherms were determined at 35° by using McBain adsorption balance technique. The sensitiveness of the quartz spring used was 20 cm/g. Specific surface areas of the carbons (N₂; B.E.T.), where not available in the literature, were determined in the laboratory.

Results and Discussion

The sorption-desorption isotherms on Graphon, which is non-porous, oxygen-free and has a homogeneous surface as well as on Spheron-6, a channel

black, which, though non-porous contains nearly 3 per cent of oxygen, are shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that the adsorption is completely reversible in each case, as the sorption and desorption branches almost superimpose each other. Similar isotherms

Fig. 1. Adsorption-Desorption Isotherms of CCl₄ at 35° on Carbon blacks.

on the remaining 3 carbon blacks which are of colour black variety and may have a small degree of porosity are also included in the same figure. In these cases also, adsorption is seen to be essentially reversible. The isotherms are concave towards the pressure axis in the initial stages indicating strong interaction of the vapour with the surface in each case irrespective of the oxygen contents

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC SURFACE AREAS OF CARBONS AS OBTAINED FROM CCl_4 ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS (35°C) AS WELL AS N_2 ADSORPTION ISOTHERMS (77°K)

Carbon	Oxygen content (mg/g)	Monolayer values (X_m) from (mg/g)		Surface area (m^2/g) as obtained from		
		the 'point of inflection' or 'knee' of the CCl_4 adsorption isotherms (i)	B.E.T. plots of CCl_4 adsorption isotherms (ii)	N_2 adsorption isotherms (77°K) B.E.T.	(i)	(ii)
<i>Carbon Black</i>						
Elf-O	40.4	115.0	94.7	171	167	187
Spheron-6	30.8	80.0	75.8	120	116	110
Mogul	78.9	175.0	125.2	301	254	181
Mogul-A	71.1	160.5	131.8	221	232	191
Graphon	nil	60.0	56.4	86	87	82
<i>Active Carbon</i>						
A	10.7	560	489.9	1093	812	710
B	9.4	470	414.1	987	682	601
D	11.5	535	471.7	821	776	684
E	8.3	210	166.6	505	304	242
G	12.9	444	382.9	897	644	555
H	7.2	555	464.1	912	805	673

of the carbons (cf. Table 1.). It is also observed that the isotherms resemble Type II of the well known classification⁶. The data, therefore, should permit the application of B.E.T. equation.

The adsorption, after a sharp initial rise, proceeds by exceedingly small amounts at successive increments of relative pressure till a point of inflection is approached at which the amount of adsorption starts rising rapidly indicating completion of a monolayer and commencement of a subsequent layer. The point of inflection is seen to occur at a stage at which the value of relative vapour pressure (p/p_0) is close to 0.6 in most cases.

The B.E.T. plots of these isotherms are shown in Fig. 2. Most of the points are seen to fit on a straight line up to $p/p_0 \approx 0.26$, as required. The values of X_m , the amount required to form a monolayer, as calculated from the slopes and intercepts of these plots in the usual way, are seen to be of the same order as the amounts of carbon tetrachloride adsorbed at the points of inflection of their respective isotherms (Fig. 1). This is shown by the data given in Table 1.

Assuming the point of inflection to correspond to completion of a monomolecular layer and taking molecular area of carbon tetrachloride to be $36.6\text{\AA}^2$, the values for specific surface area were calculated. These are included in Table 1 along with the nitrogen values obtained by the conventional B. E. T. technique. The agreement is seen to be fairly close.

The isotherms on the various porous (activated) carbons, plotted in Fig. 3, also do not show any significant hysteresis. This may be partly, at least,

 Fig. 2. B. E. T. plots of CCl_4 Adsorption Isotherms on Carbon blacks.

due to rather large molecular dimensions of carbon tetrachloride. It is well realised⁷ that the magnitude of hysteresis decreases with increase in molecular thickness of the adsorbate.

The isotherms on activated carbons A, B, D, H and G show a steep rise at the very outset indicating strong surface interactions, and a sharp break even at such a low relative vapour pressure (r. v. p.) as 0.1. Beyond that there is a small, though significant and continuous pick up of the vapour at

Fig. 3. Adsorption-Desorption Isotherms of CCl_4 at 35° on Activated carbons.

increasing pressures which may be due to formation of subsequent layer or partial filling of the transitional pores. The isotherms are not L-shaped and cannot be described as of Type I. These lie, in fact, in between Type I and Type II. This is due to the presence of transitional porosity in most of the activated carbons, as a result of which the tendency for pore filling is greater than that for formation of a subsequent adsorbed layer.

The isotherms on the activated carbon E, however, appears to be of Type II and hence closer to those on carbon blacks than to those on the rest of the activated carbons. This carbon is known to have much less developed pore structure which is also reflected in its rather low nitrogen area (cf. Table 1). The bulk of the porous network in this case, evidently, remains inaccessible to CCl_4 molecules and hence the adsorbent system behaves

more like a colour black (Mogul, etc.) than a normal activated carbon.

Taking the knee of each isotherm (Fig. 3) to correspond to completion of a monolayer and $36.6\text{\AA}^2$ as the molecular area of CCl_4 , the specific surface areas of the various activated carbons were calculated in the usual way. These results together with the corresponding nitrogen values are included in Table 1. It is seen that an appreciable fraction of nitrogen area remains inaccessible to carbon tetrachloride vapour. Adsorption in this case, therefore, appears to be subject to molecular sieve action. The fraction of the surface that remains inaccessible is seen to vary between 5 per cent, as in the case of carbon D, to 40 per cent, as in the case of carbon E. It appears that the frequency of ultrafine micropores which remain inaccessible to carbon tetrachloride vapour in the case of these carbons decreases in the order: $E > B > G > A > H > D$.

It may be concluded from the data presented in this paper that while sorption of carbon tetrachloride in the case of carbon blacks has a significance in giving an estimate of specific surface area, its relevance in the case of porous carbons is limited to approximation of relative proportion of ultrafine pores in the porous network of these systems.

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